

THE ROLE OF TEACHING HISTORY IN EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM

Ostonaqulov Mavlonberdi G'ayrat o'g'li

Student of 73-20 group, the 3rd year of History direction Socio-economic
Faculty, Gulistan State University

Annotation: The past and historical memory have been at the center of attention throughout human history. In this article, the characteristics of the development of the history teaching methodology in accordance with the human development are analyzed based on local and foreign sources. In addition, this article discusses the role of history education in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism.

Keywords: patriotism, history, historiography, history teaching methodology, historical thinking, historical memory.

Introduction: The past and historical memory have been in the center of attention in all periods of human history. As a result of this attention, answers to many questions related to historical events, persons and processes were sought through scientific research and experiment. This process became the basis for the emergence of historiography, when people began to write down what happened in the past. History teaching means the process of providing knowledge to students through historical material, educating them in the spirit of national independence, and the process by which it is necessary to carry out the tasks of perfection, the process of mental (internal) and educational actions (external) of teachers and students. The content of the history course means, first of all, it is envisaged that students will acquire the system of educational methods, skills and qualifications in the field of using the knowledge they have acquired from historical materials, including the simplest forms of scientific research, in addition, scope of historical knowledge defined in the history program, educational material: its original content.

In the scientific research of history and historical processes, the political-historical situation and the main reasons and characteristics of their occurrence, a comprehensive analysis is considered a major factor in the emergence of historical truth. Especially in historical scientific works created in different periods, different approaches and opinions of authors to research issues, different conclusions, their deep scientific analysis and making the most correct conclusions based on historicity, scientificity and objectivity are among the important tasks facing today's historians. Today, students studying in the field of history should understand the methods of mastering such as the usage of historical works, their analysis, the methods of historical research to know the effectiveness of their usage, and the ways to achieve scientific-historical truth.

When studying the reasons for the emergence of compulsory education, it can be seen that the history lesson played an important role in fulfilling the tasks assigned to education in that period. The lessons of history played an important role in training the obedient and coherent minded individuals needed by the army, government and industrial institutions. In this context, the beginning of teaching history as a systematic lesson was taught in the early 19th century in modern educational institutions to fulfill the purpose of educating the general public. During this period, history was taught for a very long time mainly for the purpose of developing national identity and educating obedient people. Before the Second World War, history lessons were conducted on the basis of inculcation of culture, in order to educate obedient and good citizens. However, during this period, the idea that education could play a role in democratization, the importance of human rights and the prevention of wars changed the concept of teaching history. In addition, technological and economic changes have made life more complex and the skills and abilities that people need to possess have diversified. These events demanded a revision of the traditional history lesson. In the late 1960s, history lessons in England were criticized for being based on names, numbers, and elements. The debate

became so heated that some people suggested that the history course should be removed from the curriculum because it did not prepare students for life in the conditions of the day. In the late 1960s, particularly in England, criticism led to extensive research into how history teaching could prepare the learner for everyday life beyond historical knowledge and attitudes. Social surveys were conducted. As a result of these studies, it was determined what skills learners can acquire through history lessons. In other words, the study played an important role in showing how the history lesson can be connected with modern life. Research in the field of history teaching in England continued in the 1970s. In England, the "School Assembly History" project was implemented and this project played a particularly important role in imparting practical skills and competences in the history lesson among students. Through this project, it has been demonstrated that history teaching should be based on research, inquiry, evaluation of evidence and drawing conclusions through evaluated evidence. In schools, learning about the past by having students conduct inquiry-based research and evaluate evidence like detectives has been found to be effective. Thus, it was achieved that students acquire basic skills such as scientific thinking and determining the scientific basis of the information given to them, as well as studying the past. In England, this process called "New History Teaching" continued rapidly in the 1980s and 1990s. Research into the understanding that a history course should prepare students for everyday life has continued, especially in recent years in Canada and the United States. Efforts to learn from primary sources with a sense of historical events brought "historical thinking skills" to the agenda. By the 2000s, the increasingly important historical thinking skills were used as one of the most effective, effective, and creative ways to learn history. Historical thinking skills are grouped into five categories based on research and understanding of historical knowledge.

- chronological thinking;
- historical understanding;

- historical analysis and interpretation;
- historical research;
- historical issues, analysis and decision-making.

As mentioned above, significant changes have taken place in the content and goals of history lessons, which began to enter formal educational institutions from the 19th century. As the well-known methodologist A.I. Strajev said: "The method of teaching history consists of these logical practices on historical material." It is sometimes recommended to classify teaching methods according to the level of students' cognitive activity and activity. This distinction refers more to the general nature of teaching than to teaching methods. In the 60s, history teaching methods and their classification were decided differently. Methodist A.I. Strajev says that "the organization, methods and tools of history teaching serve to implement certain educational tasks of the science of history." However, he also allows uncertainty in the matter, making the main methods of teaching the method of studying the historical process itself. A.I. Strajev recommends the following teaching methods:

- methods of studying historical facts;
- methods of studying chronology;
- methods of studying local historical events;
- methods of formation of basic historical concepts;
- methods of studying cause-and-effect relationships;
- methods of revealing the laws of the historical process.

It is known that history is a process of teaching and learning. Methodist A. Strajev's classification also shows that he considers only the teacher's teaching of the students, does not take into account the organization of the students' learning and the teacher's leadership of their learning. Prominent Methodist V.G. Kartsev takes a different approach in this matter. He bases the system of methods not on the signs of an educational character ("Declaration method", "method of inquiry") and general didactic tasks ("the method of studying the material", "method of reinforcement",

"method of checking knowledge" and others), but on the students' knowledge of historical events. Methodology is the basis of the theory of methods, that is, the transition from live observation to abstract thinking and from it to practice. As for the subject of history, it deals with the events that happened before. The topics in the history curriculum are usually far removed from the students' everyday lives and experiences. Although there are many historical relics and materials from the past to the present around us, history can be found as an abstract subject in its content. Because of this feature of the history lesson, especially young students have trouble understanding events that happened long before their time. In other words, because of the attempt to teach history without relating it to the present, some students find the history lesson boring, confusing, and a series of numbers, figures, and objects.

Conclusion: It is stated above it can be concluded that one of the most important elements we use to bring our past to the present is the historical setting. A historic environment has many elements, such as buildings, roads, castles, historical events, and open spaces with historic sites. In addition, memoirs, letters, maps, newspapers, plans, postcards, stamps, coins, paintings, books and historical objects are elements that contribute to the teaching of history. History lessons can be made more accurate and effective through the effective use of historical environments and objects in history lessons. One of the ways to bring history to the present in history lessons and make these lessons more understandable and interesting is to prepare materials for the lesson content and use appropriate educational technologies.

REFERENCES:

1. F. Sh. Akchaev. Innovative technologies in teaching history. Educational and methodological guide. Jizzakh-2014. p. 8.
2. A. Harris, Teaching and Learning in the Effective School. Aldershot: Ashgate, 1999. –p.401.

3. I.S. Joldasov. From the history of the development of the methodology of teaching history. "Science and Education" Scientific Journal. August 2020 / Volume 1 Issue 5.196-p.
4. Jalolov Jamal. Methodology of foreign language teaching. "Teacher" publishing house, Tashkent - 2012.